

ESTIMATION OF LEAD : GRAVIMETRIC ANALYSIS WITH PHENYLARSONIC ACID

BY ANIL KUMAR MAJUMDAR AND RAMENDRA NATH SEN SARMA

Phenylarsonic acid can be utilised as a reagent for the estimation of lead in presence of alkali and alkaline earth metals over a pH range of 6.8 to 7.4. Alkali metals and calcium coprecipitate when present over a certain amount. Coprecipitation of calcium is avoided by double precipitation.

The reagent phenylarsonic acid was used for the estimation of bismuth in presence of a large number of elements (Majumdar, this *Journal*, 1944, 21, 119, 187, 188 ; 1945, 22, 313 ; Majumdar and Sen Sarma, *ibid.*, 1949, 26, 477). With this reagent, lead has been found to give a precipitate which is slightly soluble in cold, but more so in hot water. The product is of a definite composition when the lead is precipitated over a pH range of 6.8 to 7.4. At a lower pH than 6.8 the precipitation is incomplete and at a pH higher than 7.4, the lead though completely precipitated, the salt formed is not of definite composition. When present over a certain amount, the alkali metals coprecipitate but when present in good excess, the alkali nitrate has a solubilising action on the salt. Of the alkaline earth metals calcium coprecipitates, but this can be avoided by double precipitation. In the case of strontium and barium no such effect has been observed, and in their presence lead can be separated by a single precipitation.

EXPERIMENTAL

Chemicals used were all of the reagent quality. Reagents were (i) prepared and crystallised phenylarsonic acid of m.p. 157° , (ii) ammonia solution prepared by passing ammonia gas through cold water and (iii) wash water, prepared by neutralising with ammonia a 0.04% of the reagent in water.

Standard solutions of lead, calcium, strontium, barium and of alkali metals were prepared from their "Pro analyse" nitrates. Amount of lead present in the standard solution was determined both by the sulphate and the chromate methods.

Procedure: pH ranges.—To a standard solution of lead nitrate were added 15 c. c. (2.5 to 3 times the amount of lead) of the 1% solution of phenylarsonic acid in water and the whole diluted to 150 c. c. The solution was then heated and neutralised with ammonia using 8-10 drops of bromocresol purple indicator. After the neutralisation, the solution was heated to boiling with occasional stirring under a small flame and allowed to boil gently for about a minute. The precipitate was allowed to settle, filtered and washed with hot

wash water (4 to 5 times) by decantation and then transferred on the Gooch crucible and again washed with the wash water several times, and finally with small quantities of cold water and then dried at 110° and weighed. The effect of different pH was studied by varying the amount of ammonia. Results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Pb taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Pb found.	pH .	Error.
1	0.0504 g.	0.1002 g.	0.0502 g.	6.6	-0.0002 g.
2	"	0.1006	0.0505	6.8	+0.0001
3	"	"	"	7.2	"
4	"	0.1008	0.0506	7.4	+0.0002
5	"	0.1002	0.0502	7.8	-0.0002
6	"	0.0994	0.0499	8.3	-0.0005
7	0.0458	0.0910	0.0457	7.2	-0.0001
8	"	0.0912	0.0458	7.0	Nil
9	0.0916	0.1820	0.0914	7.1	-0.0002

The lead precipitate obtained by the procedure given above was dried at 110° and then analysed both by the sulphate and the chromate methods, results of which are given below :

Substance taken = 0.1482 g.	Substance taken = 0.1282 g.
Wt. of $PbSO_4$ = 0.1083 g.	Wt. of $PbCrO_4$ = 0.1012 g.
$\therefore$ % of Pb = 50.16	$\therefore$ % of Pb = 50.20

Mean 50.18%

The value is, however, lower than that for the normal lead salt of phenylarsonic acid (50.86). Hence, the factor 0.6018 is used for the calculation of the results. The lead compound was found to be stable even when heated to 150° .

Separation from Alkali Metals.—The procedure followed was the same as mentioned above. Results are given in Table II.

TABLE II

No.	Pb taken.	Alkali metal taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Pb found.	Error.
1	0.0504 g.	0.1353 g. (Na)	0.1010 g.	0.0507 g.	+0.0003 g.
	"	0.1841 (K)	"	"	"
	"	0.1125 (NH_4)	0.1008	0.0506	+0.0002
2	0.0504	0.2706 (Na)	0.1024	0.0514	+0.0010
	"	0.3682 (K)	0.1020	0.0512	+0.0008
	"	0.2250 (NH_4)	0.1008	0.0506	+0.0002
3	0.0458	0.5412 (Na)	0.0924	0.0464	+0.0006
	"	0.7364 (K)	0.0920	0.0462	+0.0004
	"	0.4500 (NH_4)	0.0910	0.0457	-0.0001
4	0.0303	0.1623 (Na)	0.0620	0.0311	+0.0008
	"	0.2209 (K)	0.0624	0.0313	+0.0010
	"	0.1350 (NH_4)	0.0610	0.0306	+0.0003
	0.0504	1.3530 (Na)	0.1008	0.0506	+0.0002
	"	1.8410 (K)	0.1010	0.0507	+0.0003
	"	1.1250 (NH_4)	0.1000	0.0502	-0.0002

Separation from Alkaline Earths.—The same procedure was followed as mentioned above. Results are given in Table III.

TABLE III

No.	Pb taken.	Alkaline earth taken.	Wt. of ppt.	Pb found.	Error.
1	0.0504 g.	0.0500 g. (Ca)	0.1008 g.	0.0506 g.	+0.0002 g.
		" (Sr)	0.1006	0.0505	+0.0001
		" (Ba)	"	"	"
2	0.0504	0.1000 (Ca)	0.1014	0.0509	+0.0005
		" (Sr)	0.1004	0.0504	Nil
		" (Ba)	0.1006	0.0505	+0.0001
3	0.0504	0.2500 (Ca)	0.1036	0.0516	+0.0012
		" (Sr)	0.1006	0.0505	+0.0001
		" (Ba)	"	"	"
4	0.0504	0.5000 (Ca)	0.1060	0.0532	+0.0028
		" (Sr)	0.1008	0.0506	+0.0002
		" (Ba)	"	"	"
5	0.0303	0.0500 (Sr)	0.0604	0.0303	Nil
		" (Ba)	0.0606	0.0304	+0.0001
6	0.0504	0.1000 (Ca)	0.1008	0.0506	+0.0002
		0.2500 (Ca)	0.1006	0.0505	+0.0001
8		0.5000 (Ca)	"	"	"
9	0.0303	" (Ca)	0.0606	0.0304	+0.0001

From the results (1-5) in Table III it is evident that calcium gives high results due to coprecipitation and the amount coprecipitated is proportional to the amount of calcium present. Satisfactory results are obtained in presence of calcium (cf. results 6-9 in Table III) if the lead precipitate after washing by decantation is dissolved in a few drops of concentrated nitric acid and reprecipitated by following the proper procedure after adding 5 c. c. of the reagent solution (1%).